

A list of spider species found in the Marakele National Park, Limpopo Province, South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT

This article provides the first checklist of the spider fauna of the Marakele National Park, including their conservation status and level of endemism based on their known distribution. Standard collecting methods were used to sample spiders during a survey in February 2010. Thirty-six families that include 100 genera and 135 species were recorded. Salticidae (19 spp.), Araneidae (18 spp.) and Thomisidae (17 spp.) were the most species-rich families, while 14 families were only represented by a single species. About 6 % of the South African spider fauna and 14 % of the Limpopo Province fauna are protected in the park; 21 species are South African endemics, but only one (*Cheiracanthium foordi* Lotz, 2015) is a Marakele National Park endemic.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa)

INTRODUCTION

In terms of the National Environmental Management: Protected Areas Act, 2003 (Act No 57 of 2003), the primary mandate of SANParks is to oversee the conservation of South Africa's biodiversity, landscapes and associated heritage assets through a system of national parks. In 1997 the Agricultural Research Council registered a project (DIPSA 1296) at SANParks, with the aim of determining the diversity of arachnids in the different parks.

McGeoch *et al.* (2011) recently identified five major invertebrate groups that can serve as surrogates in conservation planning and monitoring in South Africa, namely Araneae, Scarabaeidae (Coleoptera), Lepidoptera, Odonata and Formicidae (Hymenoptera).

One of the core research areas of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) is to determine the number of arachnid species presently conserved in protected areas. The South African National Parks (SANParks) are key to South Africa's conservation initiatives (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2006; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016). Species distribution data generated through SANParks and other surveys feed into the conservation assessments used to compile the Red Data List of the Arachnida of South Africa (Lyle & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015).

We report on a survey in the Marakele National Park (MNP), on the south-western border of the Limpopo province. The study aimed to determine spider diversity and generate baseline data, such as the conservation status and level of endemism of each species sampled, which can serve as a reference for future studies in the MNP.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area: The MNP is situated in the Waterberg region, near the town of Thabazimbi in the Limpopo Province, South Africa (Fig. 1). It is a core conservation area in the Waterberg Biosphere Reserve and includes the highest point in the Limpopo Province (2110 m a.s.l.). It receives between 500–750 mm of rainfall annually, and includes three vegetation types (Fig. 2), namely Western Sandy Bushveld, Waterberg Mountain Bushveld and Waterberg/Magaliesberg Summit Sourveld (Schoeman & Foord

Collecting methods: Sampling followed the standardised SANSa protocol, as described by Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2015). This included sweep-net sampling, beating, leaf litter sifting, pitfall trapping, and active searches during the day and night. This study forms part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) and took place in February 2010.

Voucher specimens: Specimens were predominantly deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC—Plant Health and Protection in Pretoria. Taxonomic constraints and undescribed species necessitated the use of morphospecies in some instances.

Endemism value (END): This value was determined based on the known distribution of each species: (6) only known from the type locality; (5) endemic to the Limpopo Province (LE); (4) known from Limpopo and an adjoining province; (3) endemic to South Africa (SAE); (2) endemic to southern Africa (STHE); (1) endemic to the Afrotropical Region (AE); (0) also recorded outside the Afrotropical Region (C).

Conservation status (CS): This value was determined for each species from a recent Red List assessment of spiders in South Africa. LC: least concern, when species has a wide distribution; DD: data deficient, through either a lack of distribution data or taxonomic resources; NE: not evaluated; VU: vulnerable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: In total, 135 species in 100 genera and 36 families were recorded (Table 1; Appendix 1). Three species were not evaluated, due to the lack of resolved taxonomy of their genera (Table 2; Appendix 1). Although the survey was conducted over a very short period, the number of species collected compares well with other Limpopo surveys, e.g. the Nylsvley Nature Reserve, where 175 species were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2009).

FIGURE 1: Map of the vegetation types in the Marakele National Park. Sampling locations: M1–M4.

FIGURE 2: Vegetation types in the Marakele National Park: (A) mountain bushveld and (b) summit vegetation.

Family diversity: Of the 36 spider families collected from MNP (Table 1; Appendix 1), the Salticidae (19 spp.), Araneidae (18 spp.) and Thomisidae (17 spp.) were the most species-rich, while 14 families were only represented by a single species. Similar patterns were found in other surveys, such as the Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar *et al.* 2009), Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2009) and Makelali Nature Reserve (Whitmore *et al.* 2001).

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of the Marakele National Park, with the total number of families, genera (gen) and species sampled.

FAMILY	gen.	spp.	FAMILY	gen.	spp.
Agelenidae	2	2	Lycosidae	7	9
Ammoxenidae	1	1	Oxyopidae	3	8
Araneidae	13	18	Palpimanidae	1	1
Cheiracanthiidae	1	2	Philodromidae	4	5
Clubionidae	1	1	Pholcidae	1	2
Corinnidae	2	2	Pisauridae	2	2
Ctenidae	1	1	Salticidae	11	19
Cyrtacheniidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	1
Deinopidae	1	1	Selenopidae	2	3
Dictynidae	2	2	Sicariidae	1	1
Entypesidae	1	1	Sparassidae	2	2
Eresidae	1	1	Tetragnathidae	2	2
Gnaphosidae	4	4	Theraphosidae	4	4
Hahniidae	1	1	Theridiidae	7	9
Hersiliidae	1	2	Thomisidae	10	17
Idiopidae	1	1	Trachelidae	1	1
Linyphiidae	1	1	Uloboridae	2	2
Liocranidae	1	1	Zodariidae	3	4

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at the Marakele National Park.

DISTRIBUTION	spp.	%
CONSERVATION STATUS		
Data deficient (DD)	2	1.5
Not evaluated (NE)	3	2.2
Least concern (LC)	130	96.3
Vulnerable (VU)	0	0
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	14	11.0
1 – Africa endemics (AE)	62	45.6
2 – Southern Africa endemics (STHE)	34	25.0
3 – South Africa endemics (SAE)	22	14.7
4 – South Africa endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	0	0.7
5 – Limpopo endemics (LE)	0	0.7
6 – Marakele National Park (MNP)	1	0.7
Not evaluated	3	2.2

Species endemism: Of the 135 species sampled, only two species, *Cheiracanthium foordi* Lotz, 2015 (Cheiracanthiidae) and *Rastellus florisbad* Platnick & Griffin, 1990 (Ammoxenidae) are data deficient (DD). The former is the only Limpopo and Marakele endemic sampled. Only one female specimen is presently known. Three species of the families Dictynidae, Theridiidae

and Corinnidae were not evaluated (NE), due to the taxonomic resolution of the respective genera (Table 2; Appendix 1). Fourteen species have a wide distribution and were possibly introduced to Africa. This includes several cosmopolitan species, such as the Araneidae species *Cyclosa insulana* (Costa, 1834) and *Cyrtophora citricola* (Forsskål 1775), *Archaeodictyna conducta* (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876) (Dictynidae), *Selenops radiatus* Latreille, 1819 (Selenopidae) and *Uloborus plumipes* Lucas, 1846 (Uloboridae). Sixty-two species are African endemics, 34 are southern African endemics, and 22 South African endemics.

CONCLUSION

Although five surveys have been published on spiders of the National Parks, this is only the second paper that contains final survey results after the SANParks project ended in 2019, following the recently published results of the Addo Elephant National Park. These inventories will not only make a significant contribution to the existing knowledge of arthropod biodiversity in South Africa's protected areas, but will also facilitate movement towards full-scale use of invertebrates in monitoring and other conservation activities.

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FIGURE 3: Two species from the Marakele National Park: (A) *Mexcala elegans* Peckham & Peckham, 1903 (Salticidae); (B) *Nilus margaritatus* (Pocock, 1898) (Pisauridae). Photos: P. Webb.

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of the Marakele National Park, listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CS) and global distribution.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DIST	
AGELENIDAE	<i>Agelena gaerdesi</i> Roewer, 1955	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE	
AMMOXENIDAE	<i>Rastellus florisbad</i> Platnick & Griffin, 1990	3	DD	SAE	
ARANEIDAE	<i>Araneus apricus</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Hypsosinga lithyphantoides</i> Caporiacco, 1947	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Nemoscolus cotti</i> Lessert, 1933	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1885)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Pararaneus spectator</i> (Karsch, 1885)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> Thorell, 1859	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	
	CHEIRACANTHIDAE	<i>Cheiracanthium foordi</i> Lotz, 2015	6	DD	MNP
		<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
CLUBIONIDAE	<i>Clubiona abbajensis</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE	
CORINNIDAE	<i>Cambalida dippenarae</i> Haddad, 2012	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Castianeira</i> sp.		NE		
CTENIDAE	<i>Ctenus gulosus</i> Des Arts, 1912	2	LC	STHE	
CYRTAUCHENIIDAE	<i>Ancylotrypa brevipalpis</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE	
DEINOPIIDAE	<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE	
DICTYNIDAE	<i>Archaeodictyna conducta</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Dictyna</i> sp.		NE		
ENTYPESIDAE	<i>Hermacha mazoena</i> Hewitt, 1915	2	LC	STHE	
ERESIDAE	<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898	2	LC	STHE	
GNAPHOSIDAE	<i>Asemesthes paynteri</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Drassodes splendens</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	
HAHNIIDAE	<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE	
HERSILIIDAE	<i>Hersilia arborea</i> Lawrence, 1928	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Hersilia setifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	2	LC	STHE	

APPENDIX 1: continued.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DIST	
IDIOPIDAE	<i>Segregara transvaalensis</i> (Hewitt, 1913)	3	LC	SAE	
LINYPHIIDAE	<i>Tybaertiella krugeri</i> (Simon, 1894)	1	LC	AE	
LIOCRANIDAE	<i>Rhaeboctesis transvaalensis</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE	
LYCOSIDAE	<i>Allocosa lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Allocosa montana</i> Roewer, 1959	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Hippasa australis</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Pardosa injucunda</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE	
	OXYOPIIDAE	<i>Hamataliwa fronticornis</i> (Lessert, 1927)	1	LC	AE
		<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE
		<i>Hamataliwa rufocaligata</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915		1	LC	AE	
<i>Oxyopes flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)		1	LC	AE	
<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915		1	LC	AE	
<i>Peucetia crucifera</i> Lawrence, 1927		2	LC	STHE	
<i>Peucetia lucasi</i> (Vinson, 1863)		1	LC	AE	
PALPIMANIDAE	<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE	
PHILODROMIDAE	<i>Hirriusa variegata</i> (Simon, 1895)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Philodromus bigibbus australis</i> Lawrence, 1928	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Philodromus browningi</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Suemus punctatus</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	
	PHOLCIDAE	<i>Smeringopus badplaas</i> Huber, 2012	4	LC	SAE
<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947		2	LC	STHE	
PISAUROIDAE	<i>Euprosthops australis</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Nilus margaritatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	
SALTICIDAE	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Dendryphantès hararensis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Evarcha ignea</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Heliophanus deamatus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Heliophanus demonstrativus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Heliophanus lesserti</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Heliophanus orchestra</i> Simon, 1886	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE	

APPENDIX 1: continued.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DIST
	<i>Hyllus brevitarsis</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hyllus dotatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hyllus treleaveni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Mexcala elegans</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Plexippus tsholotsho</i> Wesolowska, 2011	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Stenaelurillus guttiger</i> (Simon, 1901)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tusitala hirsuta</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
SCYTODIDAE	<i>Scytodes maritima</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE
SELENOPIIDAE	<i>Anyphops fitzsimonsi</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Anyphops tuckeri</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Selenops radiatus</i> Latreille, 1819	0	LC	C
SICARIIDAE	<i>Loxosceles simillima</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
SPARASSIDAE	<i>Eusparassus jaegeri</i> Moradmand, 2013	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Olios correvoni nigrifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	1	LC	AE
TETRAGNATHIDAE	<i>Leucauge levanderi</i> (Kulczynski, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865	0	LC	C
THERAPHOSIDAE	<i>Brachionopus pretoriae</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ceratogyrus darlingi</i> Pocock, 1897	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Harpactirella overdijki</i> Gallon, 2010	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Idiothele nigrofulva</i> (Pocock, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
THERIDIIDAE	<i>Argyrodes zonatus</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Episinus bilineatus</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Phoroncidia eburnea</i> (Simon, 1895)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
	<i>Theridion piliphilum</i> Strand, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Theridion</i> sp. 3		NE	
THOMISIDAE	<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1941	1	LC	AE
	<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE
	<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> Lucas, 1864	0	LC	C
	<i>Parabomis martini</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C
	<i>Runcinia insecta</i> (L. Koch, 1875)	0	LC	C

APPENDIX 1: continued.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DIST
	<i>Synema decens</i> (Karsch, 1878)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Synema imitator</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisops pupa</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus australis</i> Comellini, 1957	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus granulatus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus africanus</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Xysticus mulleri</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
TRACHELIDAE	<i>Afrocecto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
ULOBORIDAE	<i>Miagrammopes brevicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C
ZODARIIDAE	<i>Cydrela schoemanae</i> Jocqué, 1991	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Diores magicus</i> Jocqué & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1992	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Diores recurvatus</i> Jocqué, 1990	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Systemoplacis vandami</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE

Endemicity (END): (6) only known from the type locality, Marakele National Park endemic; (5) endemic to Limpopo Province; (4) known from two adjoining provinces; (3) endemic to South Africa; (2) endemic to southern Africa; (1) endemic to the Afrotropical Region; (0) also recorded outside the Afrotropical Region.

Conservation status (CS): LC, least concern; DD, data deficient; NE, not evaluated; VU, vulnerable.

Distribution (DIS): C, cosmopolitan or wider than Africa; AE, African endemic; STHE, southern African endemic; SAE, South African endemic; LE, Limpopo endemic.